

METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF POPULATION WELL-BEING

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes methodological issues of assessing the level of well-being of the population based on an integrated approach. In particular, the essence of the concept of well-being, its measurement criteria, and the principles of forming a system of indicators are considered. The study analyzes factors such as income, consumption, employment, health care, education, housing conditions, and social protection as key indicators. It also highlights international experience in assessing well-being, including the Human Development Index developed by the United Nations and the specific aspects of the World Bank methodologies. The article substantiates the possibilities of more accurate assessment of the level of well-being by combining statistical and sociological methods and integrating subjective and objective indicators. The results of the study are of significant scientific and practical importance in improving socio-economic policies aimed at improving the living standards of the population.

Introduction. In the current context of globalization and economic integration, ensuring and consistently increasing the well-being of the population has become one of the priority areas of the socio-economic policy of each state. The well-being of the population is closely related not only to the rates of economic growth, but also to the social stability of society, the development of human capital and the improvement of the quality of life. Therefore, the issue of accurately and reliably assessing the level of well-being is of urgent theoretical and practical importance.

The concept of well-being is interpreted differently in the scientific literature. While in traditional approaches it is mainly expressed through the income of the population and the volume of consumption, in modern concepts well-being is considered as a multidimensional phenomenon. In particular, the Human Development Concept developed by the United Nations defines education, health and a decent standard of living as the main criteria. Also, in World Bank studies, poverty reduction, income inequality reduction and inclusive growth are recognized as important areas for assessing well-being.

Analysis and results. Methodological problems in assessing the well-being of the population are multifaceted, covering issues such as the choice of an indicator system, the reliability of data, taking into account regional differences, and the combination of subjective

and objective factors. Especially in a market economy, there is an increasing need for a comprehensive analysis of factors such as the effectiveness of the social protection system, the level of employment, housing conditions, and infrastructure development.

This section provides an in-depth analysis of the methodological aspects of assessing the level of well-being of the population based on international scientific sources. The study paid more attention to methodological approaches, principles of indexing, and theoretical views formed in scientific literature than to statistical data. In particular, studies published in reputable scientific journals on the assessment of well-being were analyzed, including the conceptual approaches put forward in articles in *Social Indicators Research*, *Journal of Economic Inequality*, and *World Development*.

In scientific sources, the concept of well-being is interpreted in two main directions:

1. objective well-being (measured indicators such as income, employment, health, education);
2. subjective well-being (satisfaction with life, a sense of social security, confidence in the future).

Modern research emphasizes the need to use these two directions in an integrated manner.

Table 1

Main indices used to assess the well-being of the population and their components

<i>Index name</i>	<i>Main components</i>	<i>Methodological feature</i>
<i>Human Development Index (HDI)</i>	Life expectancy, education, income	Integral estimate based on geometric mean
<i>Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)</i>	Education, health, living conditions	Assessment by level of deprivation
<i>Happiness Index (World Happiness)</i>	Life satisfaction, social support, income	Based on subjective surveys
<i>Gini coefficient</i>	Income inequality	Level of unevenness between 0–1

As can be seen from the table above, there is no single universal indicator for assessing well-being. For example, the Human Development Index (HDI) mainly covers three main blocks and is convenient for comparative analysis across countries. However, it does not fully reflect differences in income distribution. Therefore, it is advisable to use it in conjunction with indicators such as the Gini coefficient.

The multidimensional poverty index assesses well-being not only by income, but also by factors such as housing conditions, drinking water, sanitation, and energy supply. This approach is especially relevant for developing countries.

In measuring subjective well-being, the level of overall life satisfaction serves as the main criterion. Scientific studies have shown that high income does not always mean a high level of happiness. This indicates the need to take into account factors such as social capital, trust, and security when assessing well-being.

Table 2

Integrated assessment model of well-being indicators

Block	Indicator group	Weight	Normalization
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		(w)	method
Economic	Real income, employment, consumption	0,30	Min-max
Social	Education, health, housing	0,25	Standardization
Institutional	Social protection, security	0,20	Indexed assessment
Digital and infrastructure	Internet, transportation, utilities	0,15	Relative coefficient
Subjective	Life satisfaction	0,10	Survey results

This model allows for a comprehensive assessment of well-being. Although the largest weight is given to the economic block (0.30), social and institutional factors also play a significant role. This approach allows for the connection of well-being not only with economic growth, but also with human capital and the quality of governance.

During the normalization process, the units of measurement of indicators are brought to the same range, and then an integral index is formed based on the weighting coefficients. This method is based on the methodology of multi-criteria decision-making and is considered scientifically sound.

The analysis shows that the process of assessing the well-being of the population is associated with a number of complex methodological problems, which directly affect the accuracy and reliability of the research results. First of all, the problem of selecting indicators is relevant. Since well-being is a multifaceted concept, it is not easy to determine which indicators are the main ones and which are auxiliary. Some studies consider economic indicators to be priority, while others pay more attention to social or institutional factors. As a result, different methodologies interpret the level of well-being differently.

The second important issue is to take into account regional differences. Average republican indicators often hide real differences between regions. There may be significant differences between economically developed regions and regions with poorly developed agriculture or infrastructure. Therefore, it is necessary to use a territorial analysis and introduce a differential approach when assessing well-being. Otherwise, decisions made on the basis of generalized data limit the possibility of conducting targeted social policy.

Another complex aspect is the specificity of subjective assessments. Indicators such as the level of satisfaction with life, a sense of social security, or confidence in the future are determined through questionnaires and depend on socio-psychological factors. Factors such as the cultural environment, information flow, and public mood can influence the responses of respondents. Therefore, caution is required when interpreting subjective indicators and it is advisable to combine them with objective statistical data.

Also, the issue of determining weight coefficients is one of the methodologically controversial aspects. When compiling an integrated index, it is necessary to determine the degree of influence of each indicator on the overall result. However, the choice of weight coefficients often depends on the researcher's approach, which introduces subjectivity into

the results. In different studies, the same indicators may have different weights, as a result of which the final index value also differs.

At the same time, when using an integrated index model, the dynamics of well-being are observed more accurately and systematically. Such an approach allows combining economic, social and subjective indicators on a single methodological platform. As noted in the scientific literature, it is precisely the integrated approach that is of great importance in effective planning of state policy, setting priorities and rational allocation of resources.

In general, well-being is a multidimensional and complex socio-economic category, and its assessment requires a comprehensive methodology. An assessment based only on GDP or income indicators cannot fully reflect the real quality of life in society. The integration of subjective and objective indicators appears to be the most appropriate and scientifically sound approach. It is possible to improve the national methodology based on the conceptual approaches and index models put forward in scientific journals. As a result, the proposed model for assessing the well-being of the population appears as an important analytical tool that serves to increase the effectiveness of socio-economic policy, reduce territorial disparities, and ensure sustainable development.

Conclusions and recommendations. The conducted studies have shown that the well-being of the population is a complex and multidimensional socio-economic category, and a one-sided approach to its assessment is not enough. Well-being is determined not only by the volume of income or GDP growth, but also by the quality of health care, the level of education, employment stability, housing conditions, infrastructure development, and the level of satisfaction with life of the population. Therefore, in assessing well-being, it is necessary to take into account subjective indicators along with objective statistical indicators. The analysis confirmed that an assessment based solely on macroeconomic indicators cannot fully reveal the real social picture. Factors such as regional differences, income inequality, and the effectiveness of the social protection system may be hidden behind the general average indicators. Therefore, the methodology for assessing well-being should be differential and comprehensive. The integrated index model allows you to bring various indicators into a single system, compare them and track dynamic changes.

Based on the results of the study, it is advisable to put forward the following proposals.

First, it is necessary to optimize the system of indicators for assessing the well-being of the population and group them based on specific criteria. It would be advisable to develop a single national system of indicators consisting of economic, social, institutional and subjective blocks.

Second, it is necessary to strengthen the analysis at the territorial level. Assessing the level of well-being, taking into account the socio-economic characteristics of each region, increases the targeting of political decisions and allows for the effective use of resources.

Third, it is necessary to introduce the practice of regular monitoring of subjective well-being indicators. Studying the level of satisfaction with life, social trust and sense of security of the population is of great importance in assessing the effectiveness of social policy.

Fourth, it is recommended to use scientifically based methods for determining weight coefficients (expert assessment, economic and mathematical models, factor analysis) when

calculating the integrated well-being index. This increases the objectivity of the results and reduces methodological subjectivity.

Fifth, it is necessary to develop medium- and long-term strategic programs based on well-being indicators and improve the system of their monitoring. This will help to increase the effectiveness of socio-economic policy and ensure sustainable development.

In general, the proposed integrated approach to assessing the well-being of the population can serve as an important analytical tool for state administration bodies. This methodology will help to conduct a deeper analysis of socio-economic processes, identify priority areas, and ensure sustainable and inclusive development in society.

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